

DECIPHER

Holistic decision-making for climate & environment

Deliverable D 2.1: Factors and dynamics influencing integrated environmental policymaking

Decarbonizing heating through EU policymaking: Processes of cross-
sectoral policy coordination and integration

LEGAL DISCLAIMER

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Scope of the document	<p>A key challenge in environmental policymaking is the adoption of an integrated approach to decision-making, for example, concerning biodiversity and climate change, climate change adaptation and climate change mitigation, or energy and water. While research on public policy has shed some light on integrated decision-making, the processes through which this paradigm emerges and operates in practice remain unclear. In this task, we synthesize the literature on political decision-making – for instance, on the advocacy coalition framework or the multiple streams framework – with research on policy coordination and policy integration to create a framework of analysis. This framework is then applied comparatively to study successful and less successful cases of integrated decision-making at the EU level. The case studies for this analysis are chosen in consultation with key stakeholders</p>

identified in WPI. The research is conducted using a mixed methods approach, combining techniques such as qualitative comparative analysis and process tracing. This Task leads to a better understanding of the factors and dynamics influencing policy and political decision-making processes concerning the environment. It will inform Task 5.1 on the development of a new decision-making framework.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Holistic models and decision-making frameworks provide the groundwork for stimulating policymaking that integrates several policy goals, for example concerning biodiversity, climate change mitigation, and energy. Besides this groundwork, other processes that are important to consider for the emergence and operation of this paradigm of integrated policymaking remain unclear. Research on public policy can help understand the factors that lead to integrated decision-making. We pose the question: What factors and dynamics influence integrated climate policymaking?

We present existing research on such policy integration processes and present three case studies to strengthen its empirical evidence base. Recently, the “Fit for 55” package of the European Union (EU) represents a suitable case as it marks an unprecedented attempt to integrate climate policy into other policy domains (such as finance, transport, and social policy). One sector with high potential for climate change mitigation is the heating sector. To address this sector, we decided to analyze the recent recast of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD). Furthermore, we scrutinize the previous EPBD policy changes in 2010, and 2002.

We perform a qualitative analysis based on policy documents, news articles, and semi-structured interviews with policymakers to reconstruct and analyze the policymaking process. We scrutinize recent policy change in the context of the “Fit for 55” legislative package that marks an intensification of policy integration of heating and climate, and we further discern factors and dynamics that are facilitating integrated policymaking for the different EPBD versions.

We find that the current recast of the EPBD integrates climate change mitigation and heating in an unprecedented way in policy goals and instruments. This followed a trustful collaboration between Directorate-Generals (DGs) within the European Commission, with interactions over several years. Yet, the process within the Commission was not designed specifically to achieve more policy integration, but can be characterized as “muddling through”, similar to earlier versions of the EPBD. The issue salience of climate change mitigation at the time of the beginning of the current legislative period secured support from political leadership for an ambitious integration of climate change mitigation into the recast text. However, aspects of social acceptance and social justice remain issues which raise questions regarding the future of the policy. Therefore, integration of these aspects into the policy formulation process could be important to consider when integrating heating and climate change mitigation into policymaking. This report ends with policy recommendations, and implications for integrated policymaking in the EU, as well as for the modelling activities in the DECIPHER project.

Table of Contents

Introduction	8
Literature Review	10
Background	10
Policymaking process and coordination in the European Union	10
Heating and Cooling	10
Processes of policy integration: Factors	11
Factors for increased integration	11
Methodology	16
Results	18
Integration of heating and climate mitigation in earlier EPBD versions	18
EPBD (2002)	19
EPBD recast (2010)	20
Integration of heating and climate mitigation in the recent EPBD recast (2023)	22
Policy changes of the current recast	22
Changes in integration outcome	22
Underlying Characteristics and dynamics	23
Discussion	27
Conclusion	30
Publication bibliography	31
ANNEX 1	34
ANNEX 2	37

LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Long text
DG	Directorate-General
DG CLIMA	Directorate-General for Climate Action
DG EMPL	Directorate-General for Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion
DG ENER	Directorate-General for Energy
DG ENV	Directorate-General for the Environment
DG FISMA	Directorate-General for Financial Stability, Financial Services and Capital Markets Union
EED	Energy Efficiency Directive
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EPC	Energy Performance Classification
EU	European Union
(EU) ETS	European Emission Trading Scheme
MEPS	Minimum Energy Performance Standard
RED	Renewable Energy Directive
SG	Secretariat-General of the European Commission
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises

Introduction

Recent mainstream economic methods for climate policy appraisal fail to include complexities and uncertainties in the nexus of the topics of climate, biodiversity, and economy. In order to implement inclusive, just, and effective policies, policy appraisal needs a diverse set of models, methods, and processes that also consider other policy domains, like social policy, labor market and issues like uncertainty. To develop policies that link different policy domains or objectives, more is needed than merely raising modelling questions. Instead, there is also a need to formulate a policymaking question, which refers to a complex process with different dynamics and factors. In order to fully embrace the impact of modelling innovations of the DECIPHER project, modelers and policymakers need to be aware of and catalyze processes that facilitate integrated decision-making.

Research on public policy has shed some light on integrated decision-making, but different academic subdomains and authors have produced a plethora of concepts and terms in their study of this phenomena. After mapping these different concepts, Tosun and Lang (2017, p. 553) defined policy integration as “a collaboration of actors from two or more policy domains in order to integrate aims and concerns derived from one policy domain into another”. A predominant approach to studying policy integration is focusing on the outcome and progress towards integration, but a shift towards more processual approaches to policy integration has also started to materialize (Candel and Biesbroek 2016).

The processes of how integrated policymaking evolves are however still not extensively addressed and requires further research and understanding. The academic literature has only commenced to understand the processes that are important to consider for the emergence and operation of the paradigm of integrated policymaking. Theoretical frameworks have been presented (Candel and Biesbroek 2016; Cejudo and Trein 2023a), and applied to case studies (Candel and Biesbroek 2018; Cejudo and Trein 2023b). Nevertheless, the factors and dynamics influencing integrated policymaking are not comprehensively understood. For example, it remains unclear what role modelling plays in enabling integrated policymaking.

Furthermore, there are only few studies that focus on recent EU policymaking, although recent efforts on “Fit for 55” and the Green Deal represent a boost of innovations for both environmental policy integration and climate policy integration. It is also important to focus on the EU, as it has been found to contribute to policy integration among its member states (Tosun et al. 2019). Moreover, there is a fairly low degree of engagement regarding the integration of climate policy into the heating system, although it would provide a large potential for decarbonization. It makes up

half of the global energy consumption, and is still fueled by a 60% share of fossil energy sources (IEA 2022).

This study therefore poses the question: What factors and dynamics influence integrated environmental policymaking? It aims to generate insights into three cases of policymaking for the energy performance of buildings and analyzes its climate policy integration. It reconstructs the advances of integration, traces the policy process and discerns factors and dynamics influencing integrated climate policymaking to understand policy integration processes better. It is important to notice that policy integration as it is applied in this study is different from EU integration. While the latter focusses on the process of EU member states surrendering more policymaking authority to the EU levels, this study focusses on policy integration of several policy objectives where the EU already has policy competences of its own.

In the remainder of the report, we outline recent research of the policy integration literature, more particularly focusing on insights into integration processes, specifically at the EU level. Then we present the multiple case study design and reconstruct the process of key events in policymaking towards the EPBD based on interviews and document analysis. After that, we present the factors and dynamics for integrated policymaking in each case. Finally, we will theorize and discuss these with conceptual insights from the literature review, before concluding with the key insights from the study, as well as policy recommendations.

Literature Review

Background

Policymaking process and coordination in the European Union

In order to be able to locate the changes in integration processes at EU level, it is important to understand how EU policymaking, and the coordination between different EU bodies work. The policymaking process in the EU involves the European Commission, the European Parliament, and the Council of the European Union. The main legislative initiative lies with the Commission, as it can propose and draft new policies. While the Parliament and the Council can propose the commission to draft new policies, they cannot initiate legislation on their own. After preparing a proposal, the Parliament, and the Council consult within their institutions on how they relate to the proposal. Then they enter negotiations with the Commission trying to reach an agreement on a final text. In the end, the Council and Parliament decide whether to adopt the proposed legislation.

For the drafting of a new policy proposal, the Commission is organized into Directorate-Generals (DGs) that have sufficient staff and expertise for the specific domains of EU policymaking. The proposal drafting process in the commission is organized in a structured way. There is a leading DG that formulates a new proposal. The responsible unit in the DG starts a consultation process, collecting all relevant evidence for the proposal. It also conducts an impact assessment, where it outlines the social, economic, and environmental impacts of the policy. There are stakeholder consultations, where citizens and interest groups have the opportunity to contribute to the proposal. Service groups are formed that involve actors from different DGs to coordinate their interests for proposals in regular meetings at different levels of management. Once the draft is formulated, it enters the interservice consultations, which is an important step and element of integrative policymaking. Here, all DGs can comment in written form on the new proposal and make the leading DG aware about potential conflicts with other policy goals of the EU. The leading DG has to respond to the comments and find a solution in case of conflicts. Within the commission, the secretary general has a special role in mediating these conflicts. Once an agreement is reached, the final proposal text is published and handed over to the Council and the Parliament.

Heating and Cooling

Heating and cooling refers to all energy that is used to either heat or cool buildings, to warm water, or to enable industry processes (IEA 2022). Its decarbonization includes making the building stock more energy efficient through thermal building

insulation, and installation of sustainable heating technologies. These include heat pumps, district heating, and carbon-free gases. For their installation and operation, they require they require additional generation of renewable electricity, and distribution infrastructure, such as improved power grids and pipe networks (Sovacool and Martiskainen 2020). Therefore, besides these technological and engineering challenges, the decarbonizing of the heating system is also interrelated with questions of urban planning. Moreover, it becomes a question of social justice for the distribution of costs between homeowners, tenants, housing associations and municipalities or the state for the renovation and modernization of poorly insulated building stock (Jansma et al. 2020). Lastly, it is a behavioral challenge to reduce energy consumption through more sustainable heating practices, such as the reduction of room temperatures, or improved room ventilation. These different aspects fall partly under different policy domains but should be considered in a cross-sectoral way by government actors.

In the Commission, most heating and cooling policy falls under the auspices of the Directorate-General for Energy (DG ENER). While the EPBD marks the most apparent heating policy, some regulation of heating and cooling is also included in the Energy Efficiency Directive (EED), or the Renewable Energy Directive (RED), the Gas Directive, or the Energy Saving Directive. Other DGs have competence to create policies that focus on heating, too. The Directorate-General for Climate Action (DG CLIMA) for example influences the building sector through the European Emission Trading Scheme (EU ETS) and the new EU ETS for buildings and transportation.

These policies are drafted by separate units within the responsible DGs. In DG ENER, the EPBD for example is drafted by the buildings and product unit. The units that are drafting the proposals in each case coordinate with other units within and beyond their Directorate-General. They consult for example economic modelling units to prepare scenarios for the impact assessments. In DG ENER this is the unit of the Chief Economist and in DG CLIMA it is the unit for Foresight, Economic Analysis and Modelling. However, the units responsible for drafting legislation also have their own modelers and analysts. Usually, the scenarios and models themselves are then produced by contractors from the private sector.

Processes of policy integration: Factors

Factors for increased integration

Factors that lead to an increased coordination between different DGs and integrative policymaking have been presented by Cejudo and Trein (2023a). They include external pressures, institutional structures, issue salience, policy cycles and entrepreneurship (see Table 1). These factors can increase or decrease policy integration at the different policy stages of agenda-setting, decision-making,

implementation, and evaluation with the different results of non-integration, adoption of goals, means and implementation capacities.

Table 1: Factors that increase policy integration

EXTERNAL PRESSURE	Crises, elections, social movements
INSTITUTIONAL STRUCTURE	Procedural rules, meeting structures
ISSUE SALIENCE	Perceived importance of content, problem framing
POLICY CYCLES	Global climate negotiations, budgeting
ENTREPRENEURSHIP	Political leadership, policy entrepreneurs

External pressures

One source of change towards policy changes that cut across different policy domains is external pressure (Cejudo and Trein 2023a). These can originate for example from social movements, elections, (climate) crises and result in a need to formulate a policy proposal. For example, Hartlapp (2018) shows, how a push for integrated policies through public interests can outweigh the Commission’s tendency for fragmented solutions in times of higher public attention to EU issues. The policy diffusion literature distinguishes between different mechanisms that can result in the uptake of external policy ideas (Berry and Berry 2018). Policymakers can learn or emulate them voluntarily, but they can also be forced by coercive measures. Another motivation is competition, in order to reach for example an economic advantage compared to other states.

Institutional structures and policy stages

For the development of a new policy, there are usually institutional structures such as procedural rules that shape the integration process. These often determine the degree of interaction, and therefore coordination between different departments. In the European Union, the Commission has the main legislative initiative. While the Council and Parliament can propose new legislation, they do not have the administrative capacity to formulate new policies. Nevertheless, the European Commission “prefers close interinstitutional coordination with the European Council”, because it relies on its support in policy adoption (Thaler 2016, p. 572). For example, the Climate and Energy package of the EU adopted in 2009 was only made possible through a strong mandate of the Council for a package integrating climate and energy policies (Bocquillon and Dobbels 2014). Therefore, the cabinet (i.e. the personal office) of a European Commissioner discusses the main themes with the cabinet of the President of the European Council. Additionally, the SGs of the Commission and Council meet regularly, as well as the Council Secretariates with the DGs (Thaler 2016).

Once the general political direction is clear, the Commission tasks a lead DG with drafting a proposal (Hartlapp et al. 2013). It can set the agenda and suggest policy solutions and coordinates the participation of other DGs. These include informal exchanges of viewpoints during the drafting process, both at lower levels of technical experts, and at higher level of Director-Generals, cabinets and commissioners (Selianko and Lenschow 2015). When the proposal is drafted, it enters the inter-service consultations, where technical experts of all DGs can give written feedback on the draft. The lead DG then has to take this feedback into consideration (Candel et al. 2023). Finally, the draft discussions take place in both in the cabinet and college of commissioners. For the relative importance of these coordination mechanisms, Hustedt and Seyfried (2016) pose that the informal procedures and interaction account more for the coordinated outcomes than formal structures, like the inter-service consultations. Despite these coordination mechanisms, the lead DG can shape the proposal significantly following its interest, choosing the constellation and number of intra-commission actors that participate in the formulation process of the proposal (Hartlapp et al. 2013).

For the coordination between the different departments, negative and positive forms of coordination can be distinguished. Negative coordination describes the goal of assuring that any new policy initiative “will not interfere with the established policies and the interests of other ministerial units” (Scharpf 1994). Positive coordination on the other hand concerns the creation of synergies between policies. The DGs are generally protective of their policies and interests against policy proposals of other DGs in the informal and formal coordination between departments (Trondal 2011; Hartlapp et al. 2013). However, there are also signs of coordination that go beyond this pattern, where actors from different DGs contribute proactively to a given policy proposal utilizing their own, limited capacities and competences, forming what Candel et al. (2023) term incremental coordination.

Furthermore, organizational reforms that rearrange roles and responsibilities within departments can also possibly alter coordination patterns (Candel et al. 2023). In recent years, the presidency of the European Commission has received a more powerful role in the coordination of policy activity within the Commission (Kassim et al. 2017). The Secretariate-General (SG) was transformed into a personal office of the presidency, allowing control of quality and compliance of the proposals with its agenda, for example through impact assessments (Hartlapp et al. 2013). Furthermore, commissioners received a less important role and the SG, and the cabinet relied more on coordination with the presidency. This top-down coordination was expected to increase during the Von der Leyen Commission (Candel et al. 2023).

In the policymaking process after the presentation of the proposal of the Commission, there are several coordination mechanisms, too. Both the European Parliament and the Council have procedures for exchange between their committees and bodies while developing a position in response to the proposal (Stroß 2017).

Policy adoption does not guaranty a successful policy integration. After the adoption of a policy, the organizations that are tasked with implementing policy problems with the policy instruments, resources, methodologies, and routines are structured in sector specific ways. Agency is distributed and many potential veto-players exist, especially in decentralized systems. Integrated policies often involve a policy instrument mix and agencies from different policy sectors. This requires a political process of conflict prevention and facilitation of alignment between implementation agencies. On the other hand, organizations authorized with implementation of policy, and their public managers and street-level bureaucrats might also possess significant capacities for integrative implementation, even in the absence of integrated policies (Cejudo and Trein 2023a).

Issue salience and problem frames

Another factor that influences policy integration is the salience of a policy problem. Salience is the level of importance placed on a certain issue (Bromley-Trujillo and Poe 2020) and can be constituted by the content and the status of the proposal within the policy process (Candel et al. 2023). More interest is triggered by specific, and binding legislation, rather than by explorative documents or green papers. Increased interest can also be created by problem framing, as it creates attention and urgency for an issue. When problem framing emphasizes the complexity of an issue and addresses sectoral policies, it implies a holistic governance approach (Candel and Biesbroek 2016; Cejudo and Trein 2023a). However, the policy beliefs behind such integrative policy frames are only found to be successful, when they appeal and are compatible between different policymakers (Rietig 2019).

Thus, sectoral and divergent problem framings of different actors lead to conflict and impedes policy integration. For example, the problem framings of the “environmentalist” Directorate-General for Climate Action (DG CLIMA), and Directorate-General for the Environment (DG ENV) differ from other industry-related DGs (Hustedt and Seyfried 2016). As a result, they narrow down and limit the scope of each other’s proposals for conflicting objectives. For the adoption of the Energy Efficiency Directive in 2012, Selianko and Lenschow (2015) show how contradictory policy frames between the Directorate-General for Energy (DG ENER) (on energy security) and DG CLIMA (on climate change mitigation) led to a lack of comprehensiveness and consistency in policy integration. The level of conflict was further lower for lower-level coordination than at the level of senior management of the Commissioners, their cabinet chefs and cabinet specialists.

On the other hand, framing can also be used to make beliefs compatible. Skjærseth (2016) and Bocquillon (2018) traced how the conflicting values of energy security and climate mitigation were reconciled in a synergetic problem framing. This way, both DG ENER and DG CLIMA could be motivated to integrate climate mitigation policy with energy policy in the Climate and Energy package of 2009. Increased interaction between the DGs can also help to align problem frames. Interactions and

coordination activities of different DGs are for example found to have increased with issue salience. Therefore, it comes as no surprise that policy output of the Commission in the Energy domain in recent years has witnessed a general increase in policy integration (Kaplaner et al. 2023). Problem framing can spill over from external governance levels. For example, from the international level, and in this way help the integrative problem framing of a minority (Kefeli et al. 2023).

Policy cycles

While salience is bound to the stage of the policy process, there are dynamics of policy cycles independent from salience (Candel et al. 2023). As policies mature, the focus shifts from fundamental debates to specific requirements or details of a policy. This has consequences for the coordination dynamics, as the authority of DGs responsible for a policy domain becomes more firmly established. Such a mature policy then faces dynamics from other policy cycles that provide different opportunities. Influential cycles include the review processes of the policy itself, following policy evaluations, but also global ICCP or CoP climate negotiations. Most importantly, the budgeting cycle can influence participation and conflict in coordination activities the most. These cycles do not run in parallel and create different opportunities for policy integration.

Entrepreneurship

Lastly, actors should be viewed as central for the process of policy integration: They are involved in mechanisms of social learning, coalition building, and policy entrepreneurs and therefore possess agency to drive integrative change (Candel and Biesbroek 2016; Mickwitz et al. 2009). Actors in leadership roles (e.g., by heads of government, ministers, high level public officials, or policy entrepreneurs) have a crucial significance. They can influence a large network of policy-relevant actors and implement integrative policy despite prevailing sectoral narratives. Sometimes, they even actively reshape sectoral narratives into integrated ones (Cejudo and Trein 2023a). However, the degree to which they specialize in a certain policy field can make them less focused on the integrated aspects of public policy (Cejudo and Trein 2023b). If veto players from existing sectoral policies dominate the policy process, they might pose a significant barrier to integrative capacities. However, not only actors having leadership roles possess the capacity to influence policy integration. There is a variety of stakeholders involved in policy processes that legitimize integrative proposals, depending on the participatory opportunities (Cejudo and Trein 2023b).

Methodology

A case study research design is adopted for this study. The cases selected for studying processes of policy integration include the three versions of the EPBD. Its first version (EPBD 2002), the 2010 recast, and the current “Fit for 55” recast. Policy documents, newspaper articles and semi-structured interviews with policymakers served as an evidence base for the qualitative analysis about the factors and dynamics that influence integrated policymaking.

Case Selection

To explore how policy integration emerges, works, and manifests, we conducted a multiple case study to distinguish preconditions for successful policy integration. We identified several policy changes within the “Fit for 55” package that mark a significant advancement in the outcome integration of heating and climate. These include the recast of the EPBD, the new European Emission Trading Scheme (EU ETS) for road transport and buildings, the revised Energy Efficiency Directive (EED), the amendment to the Renewable Energy Directive (RED), the EU Taxonomy for sustainable activities, and RepowerEU. For the analysis we focus on the EPBD; on the one hand the current recast and on the other hand previous versions of it. The 2018 amendment of the EPBD was excluded, as there was not enough academic literature available on it. The EPBD was selected, as it is the central policy regulating energy efficiency of buildings, and therefore heating. Its recent recast promises to represent a case of policy integration outcome, and therefore valuable insights into the policy integration process. Since it marks a recent case, interview bias due to memory loss is expected to be lower.

Data Collection

To establish a timeline of the policy process and the integration process, news articles were collected and analyzed. For a start, we searched the website of Euractiv for articles containing information about the “Fit for 55” recast of the EPBD, resulting in 19 news articles in the period of 2019 until December 2023 (ANNEX 2). We conducted the search on 27th November 2023 and searched the heating and cooling section¹ for news articles related to the EPBD, as well as for news articles that contain “EPBD” in the general search of the website, and targeted searches on google search. To this we added the timelines of the legislative train schedule on the website of the Parliament and the Commission proposal drafts, as well as final texts of the policies from the website of the Commission. From this we could elicit the main policy changes, major events in the policy process, as well as discerning important debates and key actors including their different positions. For the previous versions of the EPBD, we gathered

¹ <https://www.euractiv.com/sections/heating-cooling/>

secondary data from academic publications, based on a Scopus search of the keywords “Energy Performance of Buildings Directive” and “policy”.

Once we had established a rather complete overview of the policy processes, we conducted semi-structured interviews (see Annex 2) with four policy officials in the European Commission to inquire about the internal integration process and deepen our understanding of the factors that influenced integrative policymaking. The interviews on average took approximately 60 minutes and covered officials from DG ENER, DG CLIMA, the DG for Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion (DG EMPL), and the SG.

Data Analysis

After recording, the interviews and news articles were transcribed and coded abductively. In Atlas.ti, interviews were read line by line, and topics in the text that were relevant to our research questions were coded openly. In order to document recent developments of integration processes, we coded the different procedural steps for the coordination of the policy within the commission, the dynamics that impacted on the policy process, and factors that enabled or obstructed a more coordinated integration process and outcome. From these codes, topics emerged in relation to these questions. From time to time, these codes were revised or grouped, for example, when codes appeared only a few times, and differentiated in case they appeared too often. These codes then helped to analyze the two cases of the EPBD using a process trace approach (Bennett and Checkel 2014; Kay and Baker 2015).

All in all, this enabled empirically grounded additions to existing theory on policy integration and policy innovation. The comparison of the successful cases of policy integration revealed different dynamics in the processes of the successful policy integration and subsequently, policy innovation.

Results

Integration of heating and climate mitigation in earlier EPBD versions

Initiatives to regulate the energy performance of buildings date back to the Oil Crisis in the 1970s, where EU Member States adopted energy efficiency standards for new buildings, as well as research, information and financial support (Boasson and Wettestad 2013; Dupont 2016). Following these, the EU also engaged in energy efficiency measures, eventually leading up to a proposal for “a European policy for the rational use of energy in the building sector”, based on the Danish model, which was at the forefront at the time (European Commission 1984). It already included themes of future regulation, for instance a thermal auditing system, a common building code, the use of funding for energy efficiency improvements in buildings and consumer information. With the issue salience of the oil crisis fading, it was however rejected by the Council through the Member States, with the latter even dismantling their own national energy efficiency programs and deregulating the national housing market (Boasson and Wettestad 2013).

While these early initiatives mostly relate to energy security efforts, beginning in the 1990s, climate change mitigation became another objective for energy efficiency policies (Dupont 2016). Leading up to the Climate Summit in Rio de Janeiro in 1992, the EU Commission proposed the SAVE Directive, which encouraged Member States to enhance thermal insulation, renamed thermal auditing into “energy certification of buildings” and introduced a regular inspection of heat boilers (European Council 1993). This aimed at affecting market pricing of buildings through the provision of the certificates, however leaving out specific obligations to member states. Boasson and Wettestad (2013) distinguish three groups of countries regarding their efficiency policies at that time: Denmark, Sweden and Germany form the first group, who had all developed ambitious building codes and extensive public funding. A second group is consisting of Member States that have cut back their policies, or never had ambitious ones and thirdly, many Eastern European states hardly focused on energy efficiency, as they were supplied by Russian oil and gas, which was not affected by the Arab Oil Crisis in the 1970s.

During the Mid 1990s, technological research communities developed various methods to foster energy efficiency, shifting their focus to total energy performance of buildings. An illustrative example concerns the German “passive house” (Boasson and Wettestad 2013). Leading up to the 1997 Climate Conference in Kyoto, the European Commission argued that the EU needs to step up its energy efficiency policy. The building stock was presented as the economic sector having the largest CO₂ emissions. The Commission criticized that twelve percent actual improvement

in energy efficiency was missed by far, as compared to the 1995 target of 20 per cent (European Commission 1998). The Council agreed to this, which led DG ENER to start drafting a new directive on „energy performance of buildings“ which was invented to represent the cognitive shift of the technological research communities (Boasson and Wettestad 2013).

EPBD (2002)

DG ENER developed its draft rather independently, hardly being influenced, supported, or constrained by industry. This resulted from a fragmented construction industry, consisting of constructors that are highly specialized and mostly organized in small firms (e.g., architects, construction contractors, plumbers, carpenters, and roofers) characterized by national differences. Producers of building products are not engaged into lobbying either, because they create products for many other purposes than buildings and are not dependent on the Buildings Directive. One exception concerns the thermal insulation industry, which lobbies in favor of more energy efficiency, but lack the resources to influence the policy process considerably. The last group of building managers, including the larger social housing organizations, corporations and associations, did not engage much in the EPBD process (Boasson and Wettestad 2013). Overall, there was low industry influence, neither on the EU, nor on the Members States level. The EPBD proposals followed more the national policy traditions rather than industry utilizing governments as an instrument (Boasson and Wettestad 2013).

Furthermore, next to the thermal insulation industry, other external pro-climate stakeholders like NGOs or industry had low involvement, particularly regulatory impact assessments and public consultations were only introduced by the Commission in 2002. Similarly, internal pro-climate stakeholders (like environmental ministries or committees) within the Commission, the Parliament and the Council were hardly involved in the policy process (Dupont 2016).

When the proposal was issued, it included the following requirements: a common methodology for determining the energy performance degree of buildings, minimum energy performance standards in new buildings and large buildings undergoing major renovation, energy certification of buildings and the regular inspection of heating and cooling systems (European Commission 2001). The draft mostly met reluctance through Member States, and while the frontrunners were positive towards the proposal, they did not lobby for it. The disagreements centered around subsidiarity issues, which means the delegation of authority from Member States to the EU level and demanded a delay of the implementation of five years (2009) (Boasson and Wettestad 2013; Dupont 2016). Since the Parliament was more supportive of the directive, this delay was in the end reduced to two years, until 2006 (Boasson and Wettestad 2013).

The final directive then included the following provisions (2002/91/EC):

- A general framework for determining the Energy performance of buildings
- Setting of energy performance requirements through member states for:
 - New buildings,
 - Existing buildings with a total useful floor area over 1000m² that undergo major renovation,
- Energy performance certificates to be made available when buildings are constructed, sold, or rented out,
- Inspections of air-conditioning systems and boilers,

Boasson and Wettestad (2013) note, that “little power was delegated to the EU organizations” and that it was left to “Member States abilities to require technical improvements of the building stock”. Later, the EU Commission provided standardized templates through the European Committee for Standardization, but there was still leeway in interpreting the templates (Economidou et al. 2020). Dupont (2016) shows, how this policy output fails to integrate the EU climate policy goals of 2050, albeit providing a medium to high output integration, whilst showing how the development of actual energy performance even exceeds the Commission’s business-as-usual projections.

EPBD recast (2010)

In the following years, while the EU prepared for the Copenhagen Climate Summit in 2009 with the Climate and Energy Package and the 20-20-20 Framework, a recast of the EPBD did not receive much support. Only six EU Member States properly incorporated the EPBD by 2006. A green paper issued in the same year hinted towards a recast, but still met resistance by member states and industr. It also met scepticism even from market supporters in DG Environment and DG ENER, as they feared interference of the regulatory measures of the EPBD with the new market mechanism of the EU ETS. An initiative for a recast was nevertheless launched under Energy Commissioner Piebalgs, who wanted to finalize the new directive by end of his term (Boasson and Wettestad 2013).

Extending the general framework of the first EPBD, the Commission was considering EU-wide minimum energy requirements, but officials realized it would be a challenging task, so they decided to focus on improving the performance without delegating more authority to the EU. Instead then they focused on introducing requirements for ‘cost-optimal’ measures, a kind of global cost-benefit calculation, so that more long term investments would be made and therefore overall more strict and costly measures would be adopted (Boasson and Wettestad 2013). Other changes included a removal of the 1000m² threshold for minimum energy performance requirements for renovations, the inclusion of energy performance certificates in rental and sale advertisements, and improved inspection of boilers. Member states were also encouraged to increase the uptake of low- and zero energy buildings through national policies (Dupont 2016). Similar to the first EPBD, the involvement of DG Environment was low, as DG ENER pushed for an ambitious policy, motivated by climate objectives (Dupont 2016). External pro-climate stakeholders,

such as NGOs or industry this time had more opportunities to influence the preparation of the proposal in the commission but lacked resources to do so. The overall impact of these consultations remained limited (Dupont 2016).

The first reading in the Parliament stressed the need for financial incentives to encourage energy efficiency measures and required all new buildings to become zero-energy buildings by 2019. These ambitious proposals mark an unusually high involvement of the Parliament and can be explained by an ambitious rapporteur and parliamentarians using the EPBD for their 2009 election campaigns, where climate issues had a high salience due to the Copenhagen summit (Dupont 2016; Boasson and Wettestad 2013). The thermal insulation industry, renewable energy industry, and environmental NGOs also influenced the Parliament rapport considerably towards setting a higher ambition (Boasson and Wettestad 2013; Dupont 2016) The Council was less enthusiastic about these more ambitious proposals and included the term „nearly“ instead of completely zero-energy buildings, leaving its definition up to the Member States, and postponing the deadline to 2020 (Dupont 2016). Boasson and Wettestad (2013) report, how the Swedish presidency enabled the agreement of the Council to the surprisingly ambitious recast, referring to the symbolic importance of the EPBD for the 2009 Climate Summit in Copenhagen and prioritizing negotiations with member states to adopt the directive.

Therefore, important changes in the EPBD recast (Directive 2010/31/EU) are (Economidou et al. 2020):

- the establishment of a cost-optimal methodology as the guiding principle for building energy requirements
- the introduction of the concept of nearly zero energy buildings for all new buildings by 2020, which are buildings with near zero or very low energy demand that is covered to a very significant extent by renewables
- revision of the standardized calculations of building energy performance to avoid national ambiguities
- removal of the 1000m² threshold for energy performance requirements in case of major renovations

Boasson and Wettestad (2013) summarize that the first two EPBD directives therefore were mostly shaped by the Commission and the Parliament. The Commission held on to their own ideas, developed already in 1984. They were rejected at the time but implemented in later policy changes. Other directives, such as the RED influenced only minor sections of the EPBD (Boasson and Wettestad 2014). The thermal insulation industry did not have the resources to influence the proposals, but rather aligned their positions to the Commission and to inputs from technology researchers. As a result, the Commission and Parliament could however not rely on the support of the industry for their proposals and counter the Member States' resistance to resist centralization of authority for the EPBD at the EU level. Moreover, the Commission proposed measures that fit with national practices to secure support and therefore competences are retained at national level (Boasson and Wettestad 2013). External

factors from the global climate regime helped advancing the policy development, as it allowed the EU to stress its role as climate leader (Boasson and Wettestad 2013). Again, however, the recast of the EPBD was only expected to achieve the climate targets 2050 partly and therefore was assessed by Dupont (2016) as having a low climate policy integration output.

Integration of heating and climate mitigation in the recent EPBD recast (2023)

Policy changes of the current recast

Changes in integration outcome

With the policy initiatives in the “Fit for 55” package, the integration of climate mitigation into heating policies has seen a significant increase in density and intensity, in policy goals, as well as instruments (Knill et al. 2012). It therefore marks an important policy change in the heating sector, outlining concrete reduction paths for carbon emissions, building on the climate mitigation goals from earlier frameworks, such as the 2020 and 2030 Climate Framework (Interview 3).

One example is that climate change mitigation has been applied to new policy sectors, such as the financial sector, where the new EU taxonomy marks a common classification system for sustainable economic activities, for example in the building sector, that are aligned with a net zero trajectory by 2050 (Interview 2). Large building companies can therefore align their new building projects with the recommendations of the EU taxonomy to be recognizable for sustainable investment decisions.

There are also policy instruments adding density to the existing heating policy mix. In the EPBD, a new instrument is the Minimum Energy Performance Standard (MEPS). They require EU Member States to encourage deep renovations of the worst-performing building stock (Council of the European Union 2023). Before that, only average renovation targets of the whole building stock existed.

Existing policy instruments have further been made more stringent. For example, through the introduction of a new cap and trade policy to financially incentivize low-carbon heating within the EU ETS for road transport and buildings (Interview 2). While the existing EU ETS applies only to large firms consuming energy, which represent 30% of heating solutions, the new ETS also targets Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). Next to the large energy end-users, now also fuel suppliers will have to buy allowances to cover their emissions (Galindo et al 2022).

Next to the addition of new or more stringent policy instruments, policy goals also reflect a tighter integration of heating and climate change mitigation. While the EPBD formerly was predominantly considered as an energy efficiency policy that was

producing synergies for climate change mitigation, the main goal of the policy has recently shifted to emission-based energy efficiency:

I think that the EPBD originally was really not a climate policy. I think if you go back in the versions of the EPBD, it is really shaped as an energy efficiency policy. If you would go to the first version, it is an energy efficiency policy, it is about renovating your house, or the warmth that you need to put into your house is as small as possible and therefore you've saved energy.[...] We've now come to the point that says: No, your house should simply have no emissions coming out of your smoke stacks. [...] I think that was from our perspective an important evolution over time, eh maybe making the EPBD in its central deliverable become more climate policy than an energy efficiency policy. (Interview 2)

This also becomes evident in the elements of the directive. The energy performance classification (EPC) now distinguishes between renewable and non-renewable sources in energy use, and it becomes mandatory to calculate the life-cycle global warming potential of buildings. This switch to a more pronounced climate policy can also be observed in other directives, such as the EED, where suppliers for district heating do not only have to ensure energy efficient production, but also a gradual switch to renewable energy sources (Interview 1, Interview 2).

Considering all these policy changes towards policy integration, it can therefore be argued that "Fit for 55" can be considered a major policy innovation in the heating sector.

Underlying Characteristics and dynamics

Issue Salience and political leadership

A crucial factor that enabled this acceleration of policy integration was the issue salience of climate mitigation at the time of the European elections in 2019. Europe had seen the rise of social movements, most notably "Fridays for Future", demanding more rapid political solutions to the climate emergency (Interview 3). The public acceptance of climate mitigation measures was high even in the wider population, as reports on extreme events and their damages staged, in the same way as greenhouse gas emissions, even if the Paris Agreement was ratified four years earlier in 2015. This led political parties throughout the spectrum (i.e., the social democrats, liberals, and conservatives) to incorporating climate policy into their political agendas.

As a candidate for the 2019–2024 presidency of the European commission, Dr. Ursula von der Leyen therefore established an ambitious climate policy agenda at the core of her presidency, framed as "the Green Deal" and "Fit for 55". This agenda combined new policy areas to climate change mitigation and aimed at specifying pathways and instruments for existing ones, as well as raising the ambition (Von der Leyen, 2019). With a strong political frame and leadership promoting a horizontal policy agenda, the ground for the policy integration was laid out and the DGs followed the proposal without much resistance in order to protect their own turf due to the combination of issue salience and political leadership (Interview 3).

The coordination process between the different DGs did not deviate much from established patterns. In particular the collaboration between DG ENER and DG CLIMA for decarbonizing energy systems was established already since the adoption of the 2020 framework in 2008 (Skjærseth 2016; Rietig 2019). Over the years, a trustful, established coordination process was being developed, which led to the formulation and issuing of many directives containing energy policies that include climate goals, such as RED, EED, and EPBD. This indicates a policy feedback effect: large frameworks, such as the 2020 and 2030 climate goals that were adopted previously have created path dependencies to specify instruments, goals, and schedules to reach these goals.

Time constraints

A difference to usual proposals was the timeframe for formulating the proposal. Instead of the usual 1.5 years, for the “Fit for 55” package it was set to one year. Half of the time was dedicated to drafting the proposal, four to five months to the Interservice consultations at the lower and middle management level, and one-two months at higher management level at the cabinets (Interview 1, 44). This created pressure for a speedy process and resulted in extra work, up onto the state of staff members, who became overworked. This has a great impact on the capacity for commenting through other DGs, as policy officers had to balance the same task in less time, effectively creating a barrier to comment on other proposals (Interview 4). The scarcity of resources such as staff personnel or time therefore created a barrier to the inclusion of different DGs in policymaking processes and thus a more integrative coordination.

Muddling through

Exemplary for the most recent revision of the EPBD, DG ENER had the lead in the formulation of the proposal, while some of the content usually is politically pre-negotiated. At the same time, interservice groups were formed, consisting of members of other DGs and regular interservice group meetings were held to discuss aspects of the proposal, assessment, and review of the policy as a central coordination mechanism. When the draft was finalized, it entered the interservice consultations, where the other DGs had the opportunity to comment with written feedback to the draft of the proposal (Interview 1, Interview 2).

It is not that they [DG ENER] come to us and discuss with us in all detail what they want to do, though I have to say that the collaboration is very good, but in the end of the day they make their own impact assessment, [...] they go into service consultations, they do present what the kind of ideas are to put on the table, and we react on them. (Interview 2)

All in all, the process of the EPBD inside the Commission was considered straightforward and trustful, with no major conflicts and harmonic interservice consultations. The SG, who is considered to usually act as an honest broker, mediated between different DGs positions, was not mentioned in the file as if having had an active role in the process. DG ENER coordinated a transparent interservice group

process, where DGs could always express their concerns and preferences (Interview 2 Interview). Some of the feedback DG ENER received from DG CLIMA in this process was to adapt the EPBD in a way that it would become more of a climate mitigation policy. For example, through including the emission-based EPC instead of just absolute energy use. This subsequently became adopted in the Commission's proposal.

Other policies pertaining to the "Fit for 55" package, might have experienced more coordination through the president and SG, as the DGs don't have a history of collaborating with DG CLIMA extensively (Interview 2). The creation of the EU taxonomy for example involved the Directorate-General for Financial Stability, Financial Services and Capital Markets Union (DG FISMA) as a lead DG and the coordination with DG CLIMA proved more challenging, albeit even here there was a generally positive attitude towards accelerating climate change mitigation ambition (i.e., low carbon) because of the overall strong issue salience of climate policy.

This finding is in line with a study by Candel et al. (2023) who found that there are both instances of negative coordination, as well as instances of incremental coordination. On the one hand, DG ENER issued a draft on the EPBD without consulting other DGs in detail in this process and other DGs merely react on the suggestions of DG ENER to avoid negative effects of this new policy initiative for their own policy domains. Instead of an integrated approach, where different DGs would come together to address the problem of heating decarbonization collaboratively, this represented a case of negative coordination. This is also manifested in the fact that DG ENER operates its own modelling team and conducts impact assessment of its own, instead of considering to also involve modelling units of other DGs. On the other hand, there are already informal meetings of the interservice groups about major topics in the process of writing a proposal and the comments that go beyond avoiding damage, but instead improving the quality of the proposal.

A major procedural improvement in recent years for the coordination of policy proposals pertains to the development of guidelines for better regulation, as introduced by SG (Interview 2). The guidelines detail how good-practice policymaking should look like and therefore include principles for coordination, such as public consultation, the operation of interservice groups, and regulatory scrutiny board, which have improved information sharing and feedback processes between DGs (Interview 1).

Integrated framing

The time after the adoption of the Commission's proposal in December 2021 showcases how integrated framing can form a barrier to ambitious climate policy integration. The Minimum Energy Performance Standards (MEPS) that were outlined in the Commission's proposal included renovation of 30% of the worst-performing existing buildings until 2033 as a policy goal. Building heritage associations have

thereafter indicated that these MEPS could threaten buildings with heritage value that are not listed (Messad 2023). This led politicians in Italy and other countries voicing fear that this EPBD proposal threatens historical building stock (Kurmayer 2023g). Subsequently, they demanded residential homes to be exempt from the MEPS regulation. In the Council, seventeen Member States then formed a “flexibility coalition”, which sought and managed to significantly lower the Council’s ambition regarding MEPS (Kurmayer 2022b).

Similarly, a political backlash occurred against the German government in summer 2023 regarding new national heating legislation, following a lack of social acceptance, which led the German Government to withdraw its support for ambitious MEPS (Kurmayer 2023h; Kurmayer 2023e). The European Parliament did also not want to put too much pressure on citizens (Interview 3). In the end, residential MEPS received a setback in the Trilogues between Commission, Council and Parliament, leading up to the adoption of the legislation, replacing the mandatory renovation of the 30% worst-performing residential homes goal with a 22% total reduction goal across all the residential building stock by 2035, of which 55% would have to derive from the 40% worst performing homes (Kurmayer 2023 c). This is particularly remarkable, as one of the motivations to introduce residential MEPS in the Commission draft was to fight energy poverty, as lower income classes would benefit from reduced facility costs due to renovations, as they tend to live in the worst-performing houses in terms of energy performance (Kurmayer 2022b). The conflict about MEPS therefore indicates a lack of consideration of social policy and justice, as well as heritage in the policy coordination for advancing more ambitious integration of heating and climate.

Discussion

The integration of climate change mitigation into heating policy outputs has advanced remarkably for the “Fit for 55” legislative package. New policies were added to the existing policy output, as well as existing ones that were adapted particularly in terms of ambitions they set. Policy changes occurred in both policy goals, as well as policy instruments. Even policies in domains where heating decarbonization were initially absent, for example finance, were adapted in a way that they now address and influence lowering of carbon emissions from heating. For the EPBD, the current recast has seen an increase in climate policy integration. This counts especially for goals, as the main aim of the policy changed from an energy efficiency focus to a climate mitigation focus. On the instrument level, MEPS have been expanded from new buildings and buildings under renovation to the existing building stock, especially the worst performing buildings. However, authority over implementation still lies with the member states, with different implementation outcomes, and therefore degrees of climate integration to be expected. Nevertheless, on the whole, the current recast marks an unprecedented advance in climate policy integration.

A key explanatory factor for this advancement of policy integration was the issue salience of climate change mitigation that worked as a foundation for a strong political frame created by the political leadership of the Commission president Von der Leyen. The European elections in 2019 functioned as a window of opportunity. Despite the absence of novel coordination process dynamics in the process of formulation, a trustful collaboration and policy feedback loop from previous policy frameworks between DG ENER and DG CLIMA enabled an ambitious policy formulation process. The collaborative environment during the formulation process, induced a shift from energy efficiency policy to climate mitigation policy. The presence of multiple crises (i.e., climate emergency, Russian Invasion in Ukraine, inflation, and energy crisis) and the size of the policy agenda resulted in work and time pressure, which likely reduced conflicts and facilitated a smooth policy formulation. However, in the adoption process between European Council and legislation, barriers to integration of climate and heating arose in the form of a framing that highlighted trade-offs of cultural heritage and social justice. Overall, they can be considered only minor setbacks in the context of the overall policy changes.

General factors that can potentially influence policy formulation and the political decision-making process – even beyond this case – on the one hand concern issue salience, political leadership, trustful collaboration, policy feedback from ambitious climate policy frameworks, and accelerated policy formulation procedures. On the other hand, inclusion of other issues, such as building heritage and social justice presented a barrier to more ambitious policy integration. However, one can argue that the proposal text did not convincingly consider these relevant other issues, so that political opponents of the proposal could use them to lower more ambitious

carbon reduction goals. In any case, this illustrates the importance of seriously considering aspects of social justice and building heritage when advocating ambitious climate policies in the building and heating sectors.

The importance of issue salience for policy integration in this case resonates with the findings of other empirical integration studies. If, for example, policy beliefs of a dominant advocacy coalition changes in favor of an integrated policy agenda, this can possibly induce policy change towards a higher degree of policy integration (Kefeli et al. 2023). Similarly, as issues become more politically salient, the need for coordination between different actors increases (Candel et al. 2023). What is special about this case is that the presence of social movements increased issue salience, which was potentially rather adopted by political leadership of the Commission president Von der Leyen, than through an entire advocacy coalition. The case confirms results from a study by Candel et al. (2023) in that the coordination in policy formulation represents a decision-making process that can be characterized to a certain extent as “muddling through” (Lindblom 1959).

Policy Recommendations

To encourage integration of climate mitigation into heating policy, it is therefore beneficial to create public awareness through problem communication and seek support from political leadership, at best in the form of a comprehensive, overarching plan that already integrates most important issues. To pursue integration through an improved and closer coordination process could be another potential avenue for increasing integration, albeit requiring resources in terms of additional staff, something that should be carefully balanced against the utility and effectiveness of this new form of coordination (see Candel 2021).

Modelers should continue to focus on developing models that integrate different issue areas. The presence of integrated models can facilitate integrated policymaking through considering more issues that might remain unrecognized trade-offs otherwise. However, it is important to realize that not every modelling innovation will lead to integrative policy changes. As our analysis indicates, these policy changes require an alignment of different factors, such as issue salience, political leadership, trustful coordination of the technical staff in the Commission, and timing in line with policy cycles and policy feedback from previous legislation. Our interviews indicate that modelling innovations that lead to policy changes rather follow policy demands, than innovative modelling. Modelers should therefore develop their models in close contact with the technical staff from the Commission, or other relevant legislative bodies in order to make their models impactful.

Availability of evidence to outweigh concerns of building heritage and social justice could further benefit integrated policymaking, i.e., through the inclusion of those factors in impact assessment and modelling. Models that integrate and represent such issues can facilitate the advancement of heating decarbonization. Additionally,

a modelling report has a different impact depending on if it is created for the leading DG in policy formulation (for the EPBD this would be DG ENER), or one of the other DGs that can only influence the process when commenting during interservice consultations.

Another strategy for advancing the integration of heating and climate is to build coalitions of ambitious EU member states through taking up and solving concerns of less ambitious members. In this way, the proposal from the European Commission would have higher chances of remaining ambitious even in the decision-making process between the European Council and the Parliament.

Conclusion

In this study, we asked: What factors and dynamics influence integrated environmental policymaking? To be able to answer this, we examined the “Fit for 55” recast of the EPBD as a novel case of heating and climate policy integration in EU policymaking, whilst analyzing factors and dynamics influencing this advancement of integrated policymaking. Following a literature study, we presented the main themes addressed in the current academic literature on policy integration. In addition, we utilized insights from a newspaper analysis, interviews, and policy documents to sketch the process of integrated policymaking and compare it to other recently adopted or implemented heating and climate mitigation policies.

Results show that within the “Fit for 55” package, the EU adopted or implemented a significant number of new policy goals and instruments, whilst making existing ones more stringent to deepen the integration of heating and climate change mitigation. Policy integration in the EPBD has not fully materialized on every policy stage, since the implementation remains in the authority of member states, who have different ambitions for climate policy integration. The current recast of the EPBD represents nevertheless unprecedented change in policy integration output.

These changes in climate policy integration output result from a few processes. One factor for this achievement concerns the issue salience of climate mitigation at the time of the 2019 European parliament elections, resulting in an ambitious climate agenda for the period of 2019–2024. While there were no new integrative dynamics in the coordination process during formulation of the policy, policy feedback of older climate policy frameworks and the trustful collaboration established for past heating and climate legislation allowed for ambitious policy proposals through a process that can be characterized as “muddling through”. However, as this case illustrates, social justice and building heritage were regarded crucial aspects to consider for a successful policy integration of heating and climate. The setback of climate policy ambition in the EPBD indicates a demand for a closer consideration of these factors in policymaking, but not least also in and through modelling activities.

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ANNEX 1

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ANNEX 2

Interview guideline

What was your role in the policymaking of the EPBD?

How did the recast of the EPBD come on the agenda?

How was the process of policy formulation for the EPBD?

How was climate policy enhanced by the new recast?

- What factors and dynamics influenced the new linkages of climate and heating in the EPBD?
- What role did (economic) modelling play for these new linkages?

What was the process of the coordination for the EPBD? (meetings, events, conflicts, novelties)

What was the role of SG or other high-level actors within/outside the commission for coordination?

To what extent is linkage of climate and heating innovative with regards to policies worldwide?